

Effect of Polya’s Problem-Solving Model on Interest in Algebra among Secondary School Students in Minna Metropolis, Niger State.

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of Polya’s problem-solving model (PPSM) on interest in algebra among secondary school students in Minna metropolis, Niger state. The study adopted Quasi experimental control group design involving pre-test and post-test. Population of the study consists of all government senior secondary school class two (SS11) students during the 2022/2023 academic session. Two hundred and forty (240) students from four schools randomly selected from Bosso and Chanchaga local government areas were used as sample. Algebraic Word Performance Test (AWPT) was used to measure the students’ interest level. It was validated by experts from Department of Science Education. After pilot testing, Cronbach’s Alpha was used to ascertain the internal consistency and the reliability coefficient was 0.82. Two research questions were raised and answered, and two null hypotheses were tested. Descriptive statistics of mean rank, and sum of mean rank was used to answer the research questions while Mann-Whitney U-test was the statistical tool used for testing the hypotheses at 0.05 confidence level. The result revealed that: significant difference exists between the mean interest level of the students in the experimental group and those in the control group. Based on these findings, it was concluded that Polya’s problem-solving model enhanced the interest of students in secondary school. The researcher recommends that Polya problem solving model should be used to help secondary school learners learn effectively. Secondly, workshops seminars and conferences should be organized by MOE, MAN, and STAN to train teachers on how to teach algebraic word problem using Polya’s problem-solving model.

Keywords: Polya’s problem-solving model, interest, conventional method, gender.

Introduction

Students view mathematics with a negative response, even though mathematics is beneficial for students’ lives. By learning mathematics, students can master the concepts and implementation of mathematics correctly in their lives. For this reason, it takes much mastery of mathematics concepts as the basis for solving various mathematical problems (Isroil et al., 2017; Fasha et al., 2018). In fact, many students find it difficult to understand mathematical concepts because the lessons are abstract and difficult to understand (Heryan, 2018). Jusra and Ramadhani (2022) added that this view occurs because students cannot use their abilities when solving mathematical problem correctly and precisely. Babatunde, Abdulrahim, Muhammadu and Zakariyya (2018), noted that algebra is a very technical and abstract aspect of mathematics which is always difficult for students to understand, which eventually makes students to memorize and leaning would not take place. As to arouse the interest of the students, it then becomes the duty of the teacher to teach mathematics in a way that will encourage the understanding of the required basic structure of mathematics. One way of achieving this is through a careful and thoughtful selection of appropriate teaching strategy (problem solving strategy) that will help students in understanding mathematics concepts especially in algebraic word problem rather than passive reception of ideas.

The Polya’s problem-solving model is a four-step process. Polya (1957) set out his summary of the core verbal steps in problem solving thus: understanding the problem, devise a plan, carry out the plan, and look back. The method is simple and generalizes well; it has become a classic method for solving problems. Sani (2021) reveals that a problem-solving approach to teaching mathematics defines the role of the teacher as a facilitator of learning rather than a transmitter of knowledge and the learner, as a manager and director of his or her own learning.

Ezumezuh (2017) noted that lecture method (conventional method) of instruction is the usual classroom “chalk-talk” method where a teacher dose most of the talking while the learners are passive listeners. Lambaya (2021) added that there is

need to adopt strategies that could enhance meaningful learning and improve the learners' interest and performance in mathematics. Therefore the classroom teacher should bear this in mind, using appropriate teaching model as to generate and sustain students' interest which in turn brings about favorable academic performance. Gender is another variable in this study. According to Khasanah, Usodo and Sabanti (2018), one of the differences between male and female is the brain. Female perform better than male in verbal memory and male better in spatial ability. Male tend to be good in abstraction, mathematical reasoning and more accurate on target, while female better understand concrete things, better in remembering and mathematical calculations. In problem solving, both male and female have different ways of thinking in accordance with their mathematical abilities. Yahaya (2021) defined gender as a set of characteristics that distinguish a male from a female. This work studies the effect of Polya's problem-solving model on interest in algebraic word problem among students in senior secondary school.

In the interest theory of Hidi and Renninger (2006), they describe interest as an outcome of motivated behavior because interest is developed and deepens with engagement. They define interest as a unique motivational variable, as well as a psychological state that occurs during interactions between persons and their objects of interest, and is characterized by increased attention, concentration and affect (feeling). It has to do with the desire to re-engage with a particular content such as objects, events, ideas, and tasks. Furthermore, they identified and distinguished between two types of interest to include individual or personal and situational interest. These they developed into four phases of interest development; Situational interest to include, triggered situational interest and maintained situational interest while Individual interest include emerging individual interest and well-developed individual interest. This study will be focused on situational interest. Situational interest according to them is transitory and is elicited by condition in the environment which focuses attention and generate act that promote attention, recall, task persistence and effect. Triggered situational interest can be described as a short-term changes affective and cognitive processing sparked by content. This phase is generally but not always externally supported by the environment. Maintained situational interest is a psychological state subsequent to triggered situational interest that involves focused attention and persistence over an extended period of time for content/ tasks that an individual considers meaningful or relevant. John Dewey (1938) maintained that interest facilitates learning, improves understanding and stimulates effort as well as personal involvement.

From the theoretical framework above, the construct of this study is built on the fact that when learning is learner-centered, that is leaners are allowed to participate actively in the teaching and learning process, their interest is aroused which in turn leads to positive academic performance. This work studied the effect of Polya's problem-solving model on interest in algebraic word problem among senior secondary school students.

It has been observed that many environmental factors affect a person's ability to concentrate absorb and retain information, and this is a problem because learning is hindered. Another problem is that the preferred mode of teaching is often reflective of an educator's own cognitive preference. This is a commonly ascribed belief that, teachers teach the way they learn.

Furthermore, there is the problem of poor performance in mathematics (especially in algebraic word problem) and negative attitude towards the subject. Esan (2015) is of the opinion that various factors were attributed to these poor performances which include large class size, students' negative attitudes, teachers' negative beliefs, lack of interest, poor teaching strategies, and lack of instructional materials. Many students seem to be afraid of the subject thereby losing interest. The abstract nature of mathematics is also a problem of itself. Students can only overcome these problems if they are helped to learn in a better way.

Finally, despite the parents' effort in guiding and helping the children at home in their school assignment, extra lessons and buying of learning materials, a good number of mathematics students still experience negative outcome as regards to their academic performance. The concern of this study is to investigate if the application of Polya's problem-solving model can be used to enhance the interest level of the students in algebraic word problem in senior secondary school.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this study is to identify the effect of Polya's problem-solving model on interest in algebraic word problem among senior secondary school students. The specific research objectives include, to:

1. Investigate the effect of Polya's problem-solving model on the students' interest in algebraic word problem.
2. Determine establish the effect of Polya's problem-solving model on male and female interest in algebraic word problem.

Research Questions

The researcher formulated the following research questions for the success of the study.

1. What is the difference in the mean interest level of students taught algebraic word problem using Polya's problem-solving model and those taught using conventional method?

2. Will there be any difference in the mean interest level of male and female students taught algebraic word problem using Polya's problem-solving model?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. **H₀₁**: There is no significant difference between the mean interest level of students taught algebraic word problem using Polya's problem-solving model and those taught using conventional method.
2. **H₀₂**: There is no significant difference in the mean interest level of male and female students taught algebraic word problem using Polya's problem-solving model.

Methodology

The study employed pre-test post-test quasi-experimental control group design. The study used two groups; Experimental and Control. Experimental group was exposed to Polya's problem-solving model, while control group was taught using the conventional method. The two groups were taught algebraic word problem. Pre-test and Post-test were administered before and after the treatment to determine the effects of the two instructional methods on student's interest in algebraic word problem. The population of the study consists of senior secondary two (SSII) Mathematics students admitted in the academic year 2022-2023 from the twenty-two (22) public conventional senior secondary schools in Bosso and Chanchaga local government areas Minna, Niger state Nigeria. They have total population of six thousand, two hundred and sixty one (6261) SSII students. Four schools were used as sample for this study. Two schools were randomly selected from each local government (Bosso and Chanchaga). Two hundred and forty (240) students were used as sample for the study with 60 students from each school. The choice of (240) as sample for the study is guided by scholar's view; Mugenda and Mugenda (2003), is of the opinion that a class size of at least thirty (30) students is enough in each group for quasi experimental research.

Algebraic Word Interest Inventory (AWII) was the instrument used for data collection. It was adapted from Yahaya (2021). It was developed to address this issue by assessing interest through simple behavioral indicators. AWII consists of 20 items gauging three dimensions of algebraic word interest: Positive Valence (PV), Negative Valence (NV) and Peer Group Valence (PGV). PV was assessed by 5 items and reflects the degree to which students report a positive attraction toward algebraic word problem (examples, "I love to be identified as a student of any subject that requires algebraic word problem"). NV was assessed by 12 items that is related to negative experiences associated with algebraic word problem ("I feel sleepy when doing assignment involving algebraic word problem"). PGV was assessed by 3 items and reflects peer group work of respondent with other students in algebraic word problem ("I like observing algebraic word problem activities carried out by other students"). Time allocated was 30 minutes. The instrument (AWII) was validated for content, construct, and criterion related validity. This was achieved by presenting the instruments to my supervisors, lecturers from faculty of education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. They were requested to study the instruments and certify if the questions were considered to be testing the performances of the students, check for possible errors in the instruments and suggest corrections. The suggestions of the experts were put into consideration and the corrections were effected.

AWII was Pilot tested in one of the senior secondary schools that is not part of the study sample but part of the population to further determine the validity and reliability coefficient and find out the administrative and logistic problems that may hinder the main study. It was administer for one hour. After pilot testing the instrument, the results were subjected to statistical analysis using SPSS version 20 for the reliability coefficients. Result obtained from AWII was computed for internal consistency using Cronbach's Alpha. The reliability coefficient was 0.82. The selected algebraic word problem topics were taught to the sampled students for six weeks. Polya Problem solving model was used for the experimental group and conventional method was used for the control group. Pre-test and post-test was given to students using (AWII) as to ascertain the interest level of both the experimental and control group. For the purpose of data collection, the AWII was given to the students to tick their responses. Data was collected, computed and the scores divided into experimental and control group and were recorded respectively. The students' scores from the post-test of algebraic word interest inventory (AWII) were collected for analysis. The research questions were analyzed using mean rank and sum of mean rank while the null hypotheses were analyzed using Mann-Whitney U-test at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance.

Result

Research question 1

How does the mean interest level of the students taught algebraic word problem using Polya's problem-solving model differ from those taught using conventional method?

To answer this research question, mean rank, and sum of mean rank were used.

Table 1: Mean Rank and Sum of Mean Rank of Interest Scores of the Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Mean Rank	Mean Rank Difference
Experimental	120	149.08	17890.00	57.16
Control	120	91.92	11030.00	
Total	240			

Table 1 shows the mean rank and sum of mean rank of the interest scores of the experimental and control groups which shows that the mean rank score of the experimental group 149.08 is found to be higher than the mean rank score of the control group 91.92.

Hypotheses 1

H₀₁:

There is no significant difference between the mean interest score of students taught algebraic word problem using Polya's problem-solving model and those taught using conventional method.

To provide an answer to this hypothesis, Mann-Whitney U-test of the Interest scores of students taught algebraic word problem using Polya's problem-solving model and those taught using conventional method were used.

Table 2: Analysis of Mann-Whitney U-test of Interest of students in the Experimental and Control Groups

Groups	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Mean Rank	Mann-Whitney U-test	P-Value
Experimental	120	149.02	17890.00	3770.000	.000
Control	120	91.92	11030.00		
Total	240				

P<0.05

The result in Table 2 shows that there is significant difference in the mean rank of interest scores between the experimental and control group. The Mann-Whitney U-test is 3770.000 and P-value is 0.001. The P calculated is lower than the P critical. Based on this, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Research Question 2

Do differences exist in the mean interest level of male and female students taught algebraic word problem using Polya's problem-solving model?

To provide an answer to this research question, the mean rank, and sum of mean rank scores of the male and female students taught algebraic word problem using Polya problem solving model were used.

Table 3: Mean Rank and Sum of Mean Rank of Interest Scores of Male and Female Students

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Mean Rank	Mean Rank Difference
Male	60	63.48	3808.50	5.95
Female	60	57.53	3451.50	
Total	120			

Table 3 above shows the mean rank and sum of mean rank of the interest scores of the male and female students which shows that the mean rank score of the male students 63.48 is found to be higher than the mean rank scores of the female students 57.53.

Hypotheses 2

H₀₂:

There is no significant difference in the mean interest level of male and female students taught algebraic word problem using Polya's problem-solving model.

To test this hypothesis, the post-test mean of interest score of male and female students were analyzed using the Mann Whitney U-Test statistics. The result of the analysis is shown in Table 6 below.

Table 4: Analysis of Mann- Whitney U-test of interest of male and female students.

Gender	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Mean Rank	U-Test	P-Value
Male	60	63.48	3808.50	1621.500	0.35
Female	60	57.53	3451.50		
Total	120				

$P < 0.05$

The results in Table 4 indicate that there is no statistically significant difference in the mean interest scores between the male and female students. The Mann Whitney U-test is 1621.500 and P-value is 0.35. The P calculated is higher than the P critical. Based on this, the null hypothesis is retained.

Summary of the Findings:

Based on the results from the analysis, the following were the major findings;

1. Significant difference exist in the mean interest scores of students taught algebraic word problem using Polya's problem-solving model to those taught using conventional method in favor of students taught using Polya's problem-solving model.
2. Furthermore, the study revealed that there is no significant difference between the mean interest scores of male and female students taught using Polya's problem-solving model in favor of the male.

Discussion of Findings

The result of the analysis presented in Tables 1 and 2 showed that the students taught algebraic word problem using polya's problem-solving model had a higher interest level than the students taught the same concepts using conventional method. The result could be due to the fact that Polya's problem-solving model employed for the experimental group is student centered. This implies that Polya's problem-solving model is more effective in arousing the interest of the students than the conventional method in teaching students algebraic word problem. The Polya's problem-solving model gives the students the opportunity to think, understand the problem, devise a plan, carry out the plan, and check, under the supervision of the teacher. This is not so with conventional method of teaching which is teacher centered. This is in agreement with the writings of Hidi and Renninnger (2006), they described interest as an outcome of motivated behavior because interest is developed and deepened with engagement. Wong (2019) added that in relation to mathematical learning, students' interest can be promoted by first presenting a mathematical problem that is able to provoke and confront students' prior knowledge and scaffold students to take challenges that help students gain successful experience. The results of the analysis presented in Tables 3 and 4 showed that the interest level of male and female students taught algebraic word problem using Polya's problem-solving model had slight difference in favor of the male. This means that the male benefited more than their female counterpart. This is in agreement with the words of Khasanah, Usodo and Sabanti (2018), that male tend to be good in abstraction, mathematical reasoning and more accurate in target. It was recommended among others that teachers should use Polya problem solving model in teaching mathematics mostly algebraic word problems. A remarkable notice of this study is that this model has shown to be effective in improving students' mathematical ability irrespective of gender.

Conclusion

Based on the results obtained from this study, the following conclusions were made;

1. The use of Polya's problem-solving model aroused the interest of the students in algebraic word problem.
2. The polya's problem-solving model is very effective for the improvement in the interest level of both male and female students
3. Conventional method commonly used by teachers in secondary schools is not suitable for meaningful teaching and learning of mathematics and algebraic word problem in particular.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Mathematics teachers should use Polya's problem-solving model to teach the students in secondary school.
2. Authorities in science education and professional bodies should regularly organize workshops, seminars and conferences to popularize the use of Polya's problem-solving model in schools.
3. The students irrespective of gender should be taught using Polya's problem-solving model as it enhances academic performance.

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